

Conference Abstract

Metagenomic, botanical and soil studies of burned meadows and pastures as basis for their restoration

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Abstract

The adverse effect of climate change is manifested to the greatest extent by increasing the frequency and intensity of fires. This directly affects our country, which in 2024 took second place in Europe in terms of forests, meadows and pastures destroyed by fires. Grasslands and meadows represent the largest ecosystem in the world, covering 40.5% of the earth's surface. They occupy 1/3 of the used land in our country. In addition to being a source of grass food, meadows and pastures have the potential to absorb and store carbon no less than forests.

The aim of the project is to conduct a comprehensive study of the impact of fires on burnt grassland ecosystems in the summer of 2024. An analysis of the burnt areas, localized through satellite images and fieldwork in Southern, Western and Northern Bulgaria, is being carried out at the level of soil characteristics, microbiome and vegetation that has managed to self-recover 10 months after the fire.

Establishing the species composition and structure of grassland communities after fire will demonstrate the function of burnt grassland ecosystems. The nutritional value, as well as the physiological and biochemical response to fires of the dominant wild legume grasses, which are one of the first colonizers after fire, will be assessed. Sowing with adapted local legume grass varieties as a method for restoring burnt grasslands will also be studied.

Our ultimate goal is to offer farmers and institutions solutions for adequate and effective restoration of burnt meadows and pastures.

Our first data is presented as Poster Presentation at Suppl. material 1.

Keywords

Grassland fire, soil biodiversity, metagenomic sequencing

Presenting author

Mariana Radkova

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METAGENOMIC, BOTANICAL AND SOIL STUDIES OF BURNED MEADOWS AND PASTURES AS BASIS FOR THEIR RESTORATION

Hosting institution

Faculty of Biology at Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski"

Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Supplementary material

Suppl. material 1: Poster presentation [doi](#)

Authors: Mariana Radkova, Katerina Stefanova, Aneta Lubenova, Anelia Iantcheva, Miglena Revalska, Galina Naydenova, Irena Atanassova, Georgi Kunev, Miroslava Zhiponova

Data type: Power point presentation

Brief description: poster presentation

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